

**THROUGH THEIR LENS: A QUALITATIVE INQUIRY INTO SENIOR HIGH
SCHOOL GRADUATES' EXPERIENCES IN RESEARCH SUBJECTS
AT GAPOK NATIONAL SCHOOL**

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Through their Lens: A Qualitative Inquiry into Senior High School Graduates' Experiences in Research Subjects at Gapok National School

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Abstract

This study investigates senior high school graduates' experiences, perceptions, and outcomes regarding research subjects at Gapok National School. The research employed qualitative methods to gather data from 15 participants, focusing on their reflections on the importance of research subjects, challenges faced, support from teachers and mentors, impacts on academic and career pathways, and suggestions for curriculum improvement. Key findings reveal that research subjects play a crucial role in developing critical thinking, problem-solving skills, and academic readiness among students. Participants highlighted the significant support received from teachers and mentors, which proved instrumental in overcoming challenges such as time management and resource constraints. The study underscores the profound impact of research education on shaping students' academic trajectories and preparing them for future careers. Recommendations for improving research subjects include enhancing resource accessibility, providing early exposure to research concepts, conducting hands-on workshops, and fostering diverse research topics. Practical experiences and improved time management skills are suggested to enhance student engagement and preparedness further. By implementing these recommendations, Gapok National School can enrich the effectiveness and relevance of its research subjects, better-equipping students for higher education and professional endeavors. This study contributes valuable insights into optimizing research education within secondary school settings, ensuring students are well-prepared for the challenges and opportunities ahead in their academic and career pursuits.

Keywords: *senior high school graduates, research subjects, experiences, perceptions, academic pathways*

Introduction

In recent years, the importance of research subjects in the curriculum of senior high school education has gained significant attention. Understanding the experiences and perspectives of senior high school graduates in research subjects is crucial for enhancing educational practices (Bacus & Alda, 2022).

In exploring the global landscape of research education within secondary schools, studies from various countries reveal both common challenges and diverse approaches to integrating research subjects into curricula. In the United States, Harada and Yoshina (2004) highlight the benefits of inquiry-based learning and research projects for developing critical thinking skills, despite challenges such as inadequate teacher preparation and limited resources. Similarly, in Australia, Levy and Petruilis (2012) emphasize the positive impact of research-based learning on student engagement, while noting barriers such as curriculum constraints and teachers' unfamiliarity with research methodologies. These findings resonate with discussions from the United Kingdom, where Healey and Jenkins (2009) discuss the struggle to balance mandated curriculum requirements with opportunities for in-depth research activities, exacerbated by disparities in socio-economic support. Moving to South Africa, Jansen et al. (2017) underscore the transformative potential of research projects in enhancing students' analytical skills, yet they identify significant barriers such as access to materials and mentorship, compounded by high-stakes testing pressures.

Shifting the focus to the Philippines, Bernardo, Ganotice, and King (2015) explore challenges within the K to 12 curriculum, revealing issues like inadequate teacher training and limited technological resources hindering effective research education delivery. De Guzman, Hernandez, and Tan's (2018) study on Metro Manila senior high school students further illustrates challenges including access to reliable sources and time constraints within a demanding curriculum.

In regional contexts within the Philippines, studies by Del Rosario and Robles (2016) in rural areas and Macabenta and Rualo (2019) in Region XII highlight local disparities in resource access and teacher training, impacting the quality of research education. Abulencia's (2015) findings in Sultan Kudarat echo these challenges, emphasizing the need for improved access to up-to-date research materials and enhanced teacher professional development. Reyes and Santos (2017) further explore how socio-economic factors in rural areas of Region XII affect research experiences, underscoring the role of community support in mitigating resource gaps. Additionally, Gonzales and Bañez (2020) advocate for collaborative efforts between schools and universities in Sultan Kudarat to enrich research education through shared resources and sustained partnerships, while acknowledging logistical hurdles.

By synthesizing these global and local insights, the study contextualizes the challenges and opportunities faced by Gapok National School in integrating research subjects effectively. This comprehensive approach not only identifies shared obstacles across diverse educational contexts but also informs tailored strategies to enhance research education locally, emphasizing the importance of targeted support, collaboration, and resource allocation to optimize student learning outcomes.

Research subjects have become an integral part of the senior high school curriculum, aiming to equip students with essential skills for

academic and professional success. However, the effectiveness and impact of these subjects on students' learning experiences remain underexplored, particularly in the context of Gapok National School. This qualitative inquiry seeks to address this gap by delving into the lived experiences of senior high school graduates at Gapok National School regarding their encounters with research subjects.

Research Questions

This study's primary purpose of this phenomenological study is to describe the lived experiences of senior high school in research subjects. Further, it aims to investigate different facets of students' experiences, perceptions, and outcomes concerning research subjects during their educational journey as senior high school students. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the lived experiences of senior high school students at Gapok National High School in research subjects?
 - 1.1. How do senior high school graduates at Gapok National School perceive the importance and relevance of research subjects in their overall education?
 - 1.2. What are the experiences of senior high school graduates in undertaking research projects as part of their curriculum at Gapok National School?
 - 1.3. What challenges did senior high school graduates encounter while engaging with research subjects, and how did they navigate these challenges?
 - 1.4. How did senior high school graduates perceive the support and guidance provided by teachers or mentors during their research projects at Gapok National School?
 - 1.5. What are the perceived impacts of research subjects on senior high school graduates' academic and career pathways?
 - 1.6. How do senior high school graduates reflect on the skills and knowledge gained through their experiences in research subjects at Gapok National School?
 - 1.7. What are the differences, if any, in the experiences and perceptions of students from various academic backgrounds (e.g., TVL vs. humanities) in research subjects?
 - 1.8. How do senior high school graduates' interactions with peers and collaboration in research projects influence their learning experiences and outcomes?
 - 1.9. What suggestions do senior high school graduates offer for improving the effectiveness and relevance of research subjects in the curriculum at Gapok National School?
 - 1.10. How do senior high school graduates envision the role of research subjects in preparing them for future academic pursuits or career aspirations?

Literature Review

Importance of Research Subjects in Education

Recent studies have underscored the significance of research subjects in education, shedding light on their impact on student learning outcomes and the effectiveness of instructional approaches. Gomez and Johnson (2023) conducted a longitudinal study investigating the long-term effects of engaging in research subjects on students' academic achievements and career pathways. Their findings suggest that students who participate in research projects demonstrate higher levels of academic success and are better prepared for future academic and professional endeavors.

Chen and Wang (2022) conducted a case study exploring the effectiveness of interdisciplinary research education in enhancing high school students' research literacy. Results indicate that integrating research subjects across multiple disciplines promotes holistic learning experiences and cultivates students' ability to apply research skills in diverse contexts. Park and

Lee (2021) conducted a qualitative inquiry examining the influence of teacher support on students' engagement with research subjects. Findings reveal that supportive teacher-student relationships, personalized guidance, and encouragement significantly contribute to students' motivation and enthusiasm for research projects. Smith and Jones (2020) conducted a comparative analysis evaluating the impact of research subjects on students' critical thinking skills across different academic disciplines. Results indicate variations in the development of critical thinking abilities based on the nature of research tasks and instructional approaches employed in diverse subject areas.

Finally, Wu and Liu (2019) conducted a meta-analysis synthesizing research findings on the effectiveness of technology-enhanced learning environments in promoting students' engagement with research subjects. Their study highlights the potential of digital tools and online resources to facilitate interactive and collaborative research experiences, enhancing students' research skills and knowledge acquisition. These studies collectively underscore the importance of research subjects in education and provide valuable insights into effective instructional strategies, teacher support mechanisms, and technological interventions aimed at enhancing students' engagement with research activities.

Student Engagement and Learning Outcomes

Adams and Brown (2023) conducted a longitudinal study to explore how student engagement predicts academic achievement over time, finding that higher levels of engagement, including participation in extracurricular activities and active classroom involvement,

positively correlate with academic success. In a meta-analysis by Chen and Smith (2022), the effectiveness of project-based learning in enhancing student engagement and learning outcomes was synthesized. Their findings indicate that project-based learning approaches positively impact student motivation, collaboration, and critical thinking skills.

Meanwhile, Garcia and Martinez (2021) conducted a qualitative inquiry into the influence of teacher support on student engagement and learning outcomes, highlighting the pivotal role of supportive teacher-student relationships, personalized feedback, and encouragement in fostering academic success and well-being. Kumar and Jones (2020) conducted a systematic review on the impact of technology integration in the classroom on student engagement and learning outcomes. Their review revealed that technology-enhanced learning environments promote active participation, collaboration, and knowledge acquisition among students.

Finally, Nguyen and Tran (2019) conducted a case study exploring the effectiveness of experiential learning approaches, such as hands-on experiments and field trips, in cultivating student engagement and deepening understanding of scientific concepts. Their findings underscored the importance of active learning experiences in fostering student motivation and academic achievement. These recent studies collectively highlight the significance of student engagement in shaping learning outcomes and provide insights into effective instructional strategies and supportive learning environments in educational contexts.

Challenges and Opportunities in Research Education

Recent literature has extensively examined the challenges and opportunities in research education, shedding light on factors that hinder or facilitate students' engagement in research activities. For instance, Smith and Jones (2023) conducted a qualitative study investigating the barriers encountered by students in research education. Their findings highlighted common challenges such as limited access to resources, time constraints, and inadequate mentorship.

Conversely, opportunities for enhancing research education have been explored by Brown and Garcia (2022) in their case study on innovative pedagogical approaches. They found that integrating research subjects across multiple disciplines and fostering interdisciplinary collaboration can promote holistic learning experiences and cultivate students' research skills.

Additionally, Park and Wang (2021) examined the role of technology in overcoming challenges in research education. Their research suggested that technology-enhanced learning environments can provide students with access to diverse resources and collaborative platforms, thereby expanding opportunities for engaging in research activities. These studies collectively underscore the importance of addressing challenges while leveraging opportunities to enhance research education and foster students' research literacy and skills.

Role of Schools in Facilitating Research Education

Garcia and Martinez (2023) conducted a qualitative inquiry into the strategies employed by schools to promote research education. Their findings highlighted the importance of curriculum integration, faculty support, and extracurricular opportunities in fostering students' engagement in research activities.

Similarly, Smith and Johnson (2022) conducted a case study exploring the impact of school policies and resources on research education. Their research revealed that schools with supportive policies, adequate funding for research facilities, and dedicated mentorship programs tend to have higher levels of student participation and success in research endeavors.

Furthermore, Brown and Nguyen (2021) examined the role of school leadership in fostering a culture of research and innovation. Their study emphasized the importance of visionary leadership, collaborative decision-making, and continuous professional development for educators in creating conducive environments for research education. These studies collectively highlight the significance of schools as key stakeholders in promoting research education and preparing students for academic and professional success.

Gapok National School Context

As a leading educational institution committed to excellence in teaching and learning, Gapok National School has prioritized the integration of research subjects into its senior high school curriculum. However, little is known about how graduates perceive and navigate these subjects within the school's educational environment. This qualitative inquiry seeks to address this gap by exploring the lived experiences of senior high school graduates at Gapok National School regarding their encounters with research subjects.

By synthesizing existing literature on research education and contextualizing it within the setting of Gapok National School, this study aims to provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of research subjects in senior high school education. The review of related literature lays the foundation for understanding the significance of the study and its potential implications for educational practice and policy.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a qualitative approach to explore the lived experiences, perceptions, and perspectives of senior high school graduates regarding their engagement with research subjects (Creswell, J. W., 2013). This approach allowed for an in-depth exploration of the subjective experiences and meanings attached to research subjects among senior high school graduates at Gapok National School.

Participants

The study involved purposive sampling of senior high school graduates from Gapok National School who had completed research subjects as part of their curriculum. Approximately 15 participants were selected to ensure diverse perspectives and experiences.

Instrument

This study utilized written interviews through questionnaires through Google Forms as a data collection method. This method offered flexibility and convenience to participants, allowing them to respond at their own pace and in their preferred environment, which is advantageous for busy senior high school graduates.

Additionally, it eliminated geographical constraints, enabling the inclusion of a broader pool of participants. The anonymity provided may encourage candid sharing, particularly on sensitive topics. Clear, open-ended questions were used, and opportunities for additional comments were provided. Overall, leveraging written interviews through questionnaires through Google Forms aligned with the study's objectives and participant preferences, making it a practical and effective data collection method.

Procedure

The study on the engagement of senior high school graduates with research subjects at Gapok National School was meticulously designed and executed utilizing a qualitative research approach. The study employed purposive sampling to select approximately 15 participants, ensuring a diverse representation based on academic backgrounds, gender, and varying levels of engagement with research subjects. This diversity aimed to capture a wide range of insights and perspectives.

Data collection was facilitated through the distribution of written questionnaires via Google Forms. This method provided a flexible and convenient platform for participants, enabling them to respond at their own pace and in a comfortable environment, thereby accommodating the varied schedules of recent graduates. The questionnaire was meticulously crafted to include open-ended questions that encouraged detailed responses regarding the participants' experiences, motivations, and challenges related to their research engagements.

The data collection phase involved continuous monitoring to address any potential issues and ensure the completeness of responses. Subsequently, a thematic analysis was conducted to identify recurring patterns and themes within the data. This analysis involved iterative coding processes to refine and accurately represent the insights collected. Throughout the research process, thorough records were maintained, documenting all procedures from participant selection to data analysis. This systematic documentation ensured the study's reliability and provided a valuable reference for future research or validation purposes.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical principles, including informed consent, confidentiality, and voluntary participation, were strictly adhered to throughout the study. Participants were provided with detailed information about the research aims and procedures, and their anonymity will be maintained in all research outputs.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the qualitative analysis of responses from 15 participants regarding their perceptions of the importance and relevance of research subjects in their overall education as senior high school graduates from Gapok National School. The analysis follows a systematic coding and thematic approach to identify key themes and patterns in the data, supported by a review of related literature (RRL).

Theme 1: Skill Development

Description: Research subjects significantly contribute to the development of critical thinking, problem-solving, and other essential skills.

Supporting Quotes:

"They teach us to think deeply, work hard, and solve problems."

"Enhance your critical thinking abilities and academic performance."

It conforms with the idea of Lai, 2011; Abrami et al., 2015, where they proved that research education fosters essential skills such as critical thinking, analytical abilities, and effective problem-solving, which are crucial for academic and career success. Research subjects play a pivotal role in the development of critical thinking, problem-solving, and other essential skills. These subjects challenge students to think deeply, work diligently, and address complex problems, fostering a mindset geared towards continuous learning and improvement.

The ability to analyze information critically and solve problems effectively is crucial for academic success and professional development.

Theme 2: Academic Preparation

Description: Research subjects prepare students for higher education by building a solid foundation of knowledge and skills.

Supporting Quotes:

"Help in contributing to students choosing their career path."

"Building a foundation for higher education."

Engaging in research activities in high school enhances students' preparedness for college-level coursework and academic challenges (Kinkel & Henke, 2006; Lopatto, 2004). It prepares students for higher education by building a solid foundation of knowledge and skills. These subjects provide students with the tools they need to excel in college-level coursework and navigate academic challenges with confidence. By understanding research methodologies and developing analytical skills, students are better equipped for future academic endeavors.

Theme 3: Career Readiness

Description: Research subjects equip students with skills that are highly valued in the job market, aiding in career readiness.

Supporting Quotes:

"Equip us with skills that are highly valued in the job market."

"Make their dreams possible."

Research experiences provide students with practical skills and knowledge that are directly applicable in various career paths (Brew, 2001; Healey & Jenkins, 2009). Research subjects equip students with practical skills and knowledge that are highly valued in the job market, aiding in career readiness. These subjects help students develop competencies that are directly applicable in various professional settings, making them more competitive and capable of achieving their career aspirations.

Theme 4: Problem-solving and Critical Thinking

Description: Research subjects help students develop problem-solving and critical thinking skills.

Supporting Quotes:

"Paves the way for improvements and answers to the problems."

"Challenge yourself in new ways."

Research subjects are instrumental in helping students develop problem-solving and critical thinking skills. These skills enable students to approach challenges systematically, find innovative solutions, and think critically about complex issues. This development is essential for both academic success and career advancement.

The development of problem-solving and critical thinking skills through research is essential for both academic and career success (Ennis, 1993).

Theme 5: Knowledge and Understanding

Description: Research subjects provide valuable knowledge and understanding based on facts, statistics, and reality.

Supporting Quotes:

"Provide valuable knowledge and solutions based on facts, statistics, and reality."

"Expand our knowledge and understanding about new information."

Research subjects provide students with valuable knowledge and understanding based on facts, statistics, and reality. These subjects enhance students' comprehension of complex concepts and real-world issues, fostering a deeper and more nuanced understanding of the world around them.

Research activities enhance students' understanding of complex concepts and real-world issues, fostering a deeper knowledge base (Spronken-Smith et al., 2010).

Theme 6: Real-world Application

Description: Research subjects prepare students to apply their knowledge in real-world contexts, contributing meaningfully to society.

Supporting Quotes:

"Prepare students to contribute meaningfully in building the nation."

"Relevant, no matter what career path we choose."

Research subjects prepare students to apply their knowledge in real-world contexts, enabling them to contribute meaningfully to society. By engaging in research, students learn the relevance and impact of their work, which helps them understand how their academic pursuits can make a difference in the broader community.

The application of research skills in real-world scenarios helps students understand the relevance and impact of their work (Healey & Jenkins, 2009).

Theme 7: Personal Growth and Self-improvement

Description: Research subjects promote personal growth and self-improvement by motivating students and enhancing their capabilities.

Supporting Quotes:

"Help me to be more motivated and improve my capabilities."

"Significant in preparing the students for their future academic pursuits and career aspirations."

Research subjects promote personal growth and self-improvement by motivating students and enhancing their capabilities. Engaging in research encourages students to strive for excellence, develop resilience, and reach their full potential, fostering a sense of accomplishment and self-worth.

Engaging in research promotes personal development and self-improvement, encouraging students to reach their full potential (Lopatto, 2004).

The analysis reveals that senior high school graduates from Gapok National School envision research subjects playing a crucial role in preparing them for future academic pursuits and career aspirations. The key themes identified include skill development, academic preparation, career readiness, problem-solving and critical thinking, knowledge and understanding, real-world application, and personal growth and self-improvement. These findings are supported by related literature, highlighting the comprehensive benefits of incorporating research subjects into the high school curriculum.

This study explored the experiences, perceptions, and outcomes related to research subjects among senior high school graduates from Gapok National School. The data was gathered through qualitative responses from 15 participants and analyzed through a systematic coding and thematic approach. The investigation covered several key areas: the importance and relevance of research subjects, the challenges encountered by students, the support provided by teachers and mentors, the impact on academic and career pathways, and suggestions for improving research subjects in the curriculum.

Research subjects were found to be essential for developing critical thinking, analytical skills, and academic readiness, preparing students for higher education and future careers by enhancing their problem-solving abilities and providing practical skills. However, students faced various challenges, including time management, resource availability, and technical difficulties, which necessitated effective guidance and support from teachers and mentors. This support significantly influenced students' research experiences, providing moral, emotional, and practical assistance crucial for successful research outcomes.

The impact of research subjects on academic and career pathways was profound, as they played a pivotal role in shaping students' academic trajectories and career aspirations. They provided a foundation for higher education and equipped students with skills highly valued in the job market. To further improve the effectiveness and relevance of research subjects, students suggested enhancing resource accessibility, providing early research exposure, offering hands-on workshops, increasing practical experience, fostering diverse research topics, and improving time management guidance.

Conclusions

The analysis and interpretation of the data gathered led to several key conclusions. First, research education is a vital component of the senior high school curriculum, essential for fostering critical academic and professional skills and preparing students for the demands of higher education and the workforce. However, students encounter significant challenges in undertaking research projects, underscoring the need for robust support systems. Continuous guidance from teachers and mentors, along with access to adequate resources and practical experiences, is crucial in overcoming these challenges.

Research subjects contribute significantly to students' academic preparedness and career readiness, equipping them with transferable skills, critical thinking, and problem-solving abilities essential for future success. The study also highlights areas for improvement to enhance the effectiveness of research education, including better resource provision, early exposure to research concepts, and increased practical experiences. A diverse range of research topics and improved time management training can further benefit students, making research education more engaging and relevant to their interests and career goals.

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